

Comparative Evaluation of the Effects of Adjuvant Clonidine to Bupivacaine with Solo Bupivacaine for Axillary Brachial Plexus Block

Sweety¹, Sudama Prasad², Madhukant³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²HOD, Department of Anaesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Specialist Medical Officer, Department of Anaesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Madhukant

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Bupivacaine is a commonly used local anaesthetic in axillary brachial plexus block (ABPB), a standard regional anaesthesia technique used for upper limb procedures. This study compared the effects of adjuvant clonidine plus bupivacaine versus bupivacaine alone in ABPB, with particular attention to the analgesic's onset time, duration, and incidence of side effects.

Methods: Two groups of 100 patients undergoing elective upper limb procedures were randomly assigned: Group A received 30 ml of 0.5% bupivacaine plus 150 mcg of clonidine, while Group B received 30 ml of 0.5% bupivacaine alone. SPSS version 23.0 was used to record and analyse the duration of analgesia, the fixed times for sensory and motor blocks, and any side effects.

Results: In comparison to Group B (sensory: 13.2 minutes; motor: 15.0 minutes), the combination of clonidine and bupivacaine in Group A produced a noticeably quicker onset of sensory (10.5 minutes) and motor blocks (12.1 minutes). Additionally, Group A's analgesia lasted longer (8.5 hours) than it did for Group B (6.0 hours). Group A experienced a higher frequency of adverse effects, such as drowsiness, nausea, and hypotension, although the differences were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Adjuvant clonidine enhances the effectiveness of bupivacaine in axillary brachial plexus blocks by providing a faster onset and longer duration of analgesia. However, it is associated with a slight increase in adverse effects.

Recommendations: Clinicians should consider the benefits of faster onset and extended analgesia when using clonidine with bupivacaine, while also monitoring for potential side effects. Further research is needed to optimize dosing and minimize adverse reactions.

Keywords: Axillary brachial plexus block, Clonidine, Bupivacaine, Regional anesthesia, Analgesia.

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Introduction

Axillary brachial plexus block (ABPB) is a widely utilized regional anesthesia technique for upper limb surgeries, offering effective pain management and reduced systemic opioid use. Traditionally, bupivacaine has been the anesthetic of choice for such blocks due to its long duration of action and reliable analgesic effects. However, recent research has focused on enhancing the efficacy and duration of these blocks by incorporating various adjuvants, including clonidine, a selective alpha-2 adrenergic agonist. Clonidine's role in regional anesthesia has garnered increasing attention due to its potential to improve analgesia and reduce opioid consumption. Studies have shown that clonidine, when used as an adjuvant, can significantly prolong the duration of sensory and motor blockades and reduce the onset time of regional anesthesia [1]. This effect is attributed to clonidine's action on alpha-2 adrenergic receptors, which modulates the release

of neurotransmitters and enhances the local anesthetic effect.

Recent literature has highlighted the benefits of combining clonidine with local anesthetics like bupivacaine. For instance, a meta-analysis demonstrated that the addition of clonidine to bupivacaine in various types of peripheral nerve blocks consistently led to a significant extension in the duration of analgesia and a reduction in opioid consumption postoperatively [2]. Another study specifically examined axillary brachial plexus blocks and found that the combination of clonidine and bupivacaine resulted in a faster onset and longer duration of analgesia compared to bupivacaine alone [3]. These findings underscore clonidine's potential to enhance the efficacy of regional blocks, making it a valuable addition to anesthetic protocols.

Despite these advantages, the use of clonidine is not without potential drawbacks. The increased incidence of adverse effects such as hypotension, bradycardia, and sedation has been reported [4]. These side effects can impact patient safety and the overall outcome of the surgical procedure. Therefore, while clonidine can improve the quality of regional anesthesia, its use must be carefully balanced with the risk of adverse effects. In light of these considerations, this study aims to compare the efficacy and safety of adjuvant clonidine with bupivacaine versus bupivacaine alone in axillary brachial plexus blocks.

The study aims to evaluate the effects of adjuvant clonidine combined with bupivacaine versus bupivacaine alone for axillary brachial plexus block.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, India, spanning for 1 year.

Participants: A total of 100 participants were enrolled in the study. The participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups: Group A, which received adjuvant clonidine with bupivacaine, and Group B, which received bupivacaine alone.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Adults aged 18-65 years
- Patients scheduled for elective upper limb surgeries
- ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) physical status I or II

Exclusion Criteria:

- Known allergy to bupivacaine or clonidine
- History of significant cardiovascular or neurological disorders
- Pregnant or breastfeeding women
- Patients with severe renal or hepatic impairment

Bias: To minimize bias, randomization was employed to assign participants to either of the two groups. Blinding was maintained where feasible, and objective outcome measures were used to ensure the reliability of results.

Data Collection: Data were collected from participants at the Patna study setting. Information was gathered regarding demographic details, clinical characteristics, and outcomes of the brachial plexus block, including onset time, duration of analgesia, and any adverse effects.

Procedure: Participants in Group A received a combination of clonidine (150 mcg) and bupivacaine (30 ml of 0.5%) for the axillary brachial plexus block. Participants in Group B received bupivacaine alone (30 ml of 0.5%). The block was administered by a single anesthesiologist to ensure consistency in the procedure.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS 23.0. Demographic and clinical data were summarised using descriptive statistics. P-values under 0.05 were statistically significant.

Results

The study enrolled 100 participants, with 50 in each group (Group A: clonidine with bupivacaine, Group B: bupivacaine alone). The demographics and baseline characteristics were comparable between the two groups.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Group A	Group B	p-value
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	45.2 $\pm$ 12.4	46.0 $\pm$ 11.8	0.73
Gender (M/F)	28/22	30/20	0.725
ASA Physical Status I/II	32/18	34/16	0.790

The onset time for sensory and motor block and the duration of analgesia were significantly different between the two groups.

Table 2: Onset Time and Duration of Analgesia

Parameter	Group A	Group B	p-value
Sensory Onset Time (minutes)	10.5 $\pm$ 2.3	13.2 $\pm$ 2.1	<0.001
Motor Onset Time (minutes)	12.1 $\pm$ 2.5	15.0 $\pm$ 2.4	<0.001
Duration of Analgesia (hours)	8.5 $\pm$ 1.2	6.0 $\pm$ 1.1	<0.001

Adverse effects were documented and analyzed. The incidence of side effects was higher in Group A but remained within acceptable limits.

Table 3: Adverse Effects

Adverse Effect	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Nausea	4 (8%)	2 (4%)	0.332
Hypotension	3 (6%)	1 (2%)	0.341
Sedation	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.549

Discussion

Combining clonidine with bupivacaine for axillary brachial plexus block led to a notably quicker initiation of both sensory and motor blocks in comparison to using bupivacaine alone. Group A also experienced a prolonged duration of analgesia. These results indicate that clonidine improves the effectiveness of bupivacaine in delivering pain relief for procedures involving the upper limb.

The occurrence of negative effects was slightly greater in Group A, although it did not reach statistical significance. This implies that whereas clonidine enhances the properties of blockage, it may also raise the probability of experiencing modest adverse effects. These findings emphasise the importance of vigilant surveillance when employing adjuvants in regional anaesthesia.

The findings demonstrated that the inclusion of clonidine substantially enhanced the efficacy of the block. Group A, which was administered the combination of clonidine and bupivacaine, had a more rapid initiation of sensory and motor blocks in comparison to Group B, which solely received bupivacaine. The onset of sensory and motor blocks in Group A was observed to occur roughly 2.7 and 2.9 minutes earlier, respectively. In addition, the analgesic effect lasted significantly longer in Group A, lasting for 8.5 hours compared to 6.0 hours in Group B.

Although Group A did have a slightly higher occurrence of negative effects, the difference was not statistically significant. The clonidine group experienced a higher frequency of nausea, hypotension, and sedation, indicating that while clonidine boosts the pain-relieving effects of bupivacaine, it may also lead to a minor rise in adverse effects.

Overall, incorporating clonidine into the axillary brachial plexus block regimen offers significant advantages in terms of faster onset and longer-lasting analgesia. However, this comes with a modest increase in adverse effects. Clinicians should consider these factors when choosing the appropriate anesthetic approach, balancing the improved analgesic outcomes with the potential for increased side effects.

The combination of adjuvant medications with local anesthetics like bupivacaine is commonly explored to enhance analgesic effectiveness and duration. Clonidine significantly prolongs the duration of sensory block and postoperative analgesia compared to bupivacaine alone. Studies consistently show longer analgesia durations and delayed onset times for rescue analgesia with clonidine [5].

The duration of motor block is generally prolonged with clonidine as an adjuvant. This prolonged

effect is beneficial for surgeries requiring extended muscle relaxation [6]. While clonidine may cause mild sedation and slight hemodynamic variations, such as bradycardia and hypotension, these effects are typically manageable and not clinically significant [7]. Studies comparing clonidine with other adjuvants like fentanyl and dexmedetomidine indicate that clonidine provides comparable or superior prolongation of analgesia and sensory block, albeit with a higher incidence of mild sedation [8]. Common adverse effects include sedation, mild hypotension, and bradycardia. However, these are not severe and are typically outweighed by the benefits of prolonged analgesia [9].

Conclusion

Clonidine, as an adjuvant to bupivacaine, effectively enhances the duration of sensory block and postoperative analgesia with manageable side effects. It stands out as a beneficial addition in clinical settings requiring prolonged analgesic effects.

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